

A Novel Method of QRS Detection using Time and Amplitude Thresholds with Statistical False Peak Elimination

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KEYWORDS

QRS complex detection,
ECG signal processing,
wavelet transform,
noise suppression

ABSTRACT

The electrocardiogram (ECG) captures cardiac activity through the QRS complex, which is centered at the R-peak of each heartbeat. However, accurate analysis of ECG signals is often impeded by low-frequency baseline wander, high-frequency noise, interference from P and T waves, and variations in QRS morphology. Among the various tasks in ECG analysis, QRS complex detection is crucial for effective heart monitoring and diagnosis. ECG signal processing primarily involves three key aspects: signal denoising, wave detection, and heartbeat classification. Notably, signal denoising plays a vital role in enhancing the accuracy of subsequent analyses by mitigating noise artifacts.

This study proposes a novel peak detection algorithm that effectively suppresses noise while adapting to variations in ECG morphology, thereby improving detection performance. The proposed algorithm is based on wavelet transformation and is evaluated against the Statistical False Peak Elimination (SFPE) method, incorporating median and moving average filters. Given the non-stationary nature of ECG signals, wavelet-based techniques prove to be highly effective for signal denoising, wave detection, and heartbeat classification, demonstrating superior performance in ECG analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The electrocardiogram (ECG) is a non-invasive test [1] for the heart which is conducted by placing electrodes on the chest to record the electrical activity of the heart [2]. It contains P waves, QRS complexes, and T waves. Figure. 1 shows an ECG signal with the QRS complex at its center. The signal obtained from an individual has large amounts of noise components which makes the R-peak detection very challenging. R-peaks are prominent features in the ECG signal, however, due to noise, they are quite often suppressed and cannot be detected properly without removing the noise contaminating the sample. The sources of noise are: Power-line interference, electrode contact noise, muscle contraction noise, motion artifacts, the noise produced from electronic devices, external electrical interference such as recording systems, baseline wander, and bodily sounds such as breathing, stomach, or bowels sounds [3].

All these unwanted artifacts make the detection of R-peaks quite challenging to date and though algorithms have reached quite a high accuracy in recent times. Most of them rely on very complex transformations and adaptive amplitude (y-axis) thresholding techniques to achieve such results. The main motive for most methods is to reduce the noise as best as possible while keeping the high frequency details of the QRS intact as the information of the R-peaks is also a high-frequency component whose frequency coincides with some of the biomedical signals such as electromyography (EMG). To achieve this, bandpass and derivative filtering are used in [4]–[7]. However, band-pass filters cannot adapt to the sudden variations in the bandwidth in the frequency domain of the QRS [8]. To solve this problem, continuous wavelet transform (CWT) is used in [8] which gives rise to the problem of high complexity and extensive usage of memory. Therefore, further enhancements to reduce those problems would be by using discrete wavelet transform (DWT).

At high frequencies, the wavelet decomposition provides good time resolution and at low frequencies, it provides good frequency resolution. Such types of decomposition are used in [9]–[13] for denoising purposes while the work in [14] presented an overview of the types of wavelets suitable for ECG noise reduction. The process is further enhanced in [15] by making DWT tunable which is a great way to account for records from different databases. However, using

wavelet transform requires several filters and that will make the process computationally challenging. Another method that is quite effective in envelope detection is Hilbert transform (HT). This was used in [16] and [17] with each having a separate preprocessing and decision stage. This method was good as it adapts to morphological changes in the ECG signal but was susceptible to high amounts of noise. A combination of both HT and DWT is found in [18], [19], while the work in [20] has used least-mean-squares (LMS) adaptive filtering along with DWT to reduce noise and detect R-peaks. An overview of adaptive filters was given in [21] that compares different varieties of LMS and recursive-leastsquares (RLS) filters based on their abilities to detect R peaks by adaptively reducing the noise while the work in [22] presents two different modes of adaptive filters which are used for extraction purposes. Empirical mode decomposition (EMD) is another outstanding method to reduce noise. It was used in [23], [24] and was highly effective in minimizing all categories of noise to simplify the detection stage. EMD can adapt effectively to all the changes of morphologies of a wide variety of signals but is a highly complex and memory consuming transformation. An upgrade of EMD is called the Hilbert-Huang transformation [25] which uses Hilbert transform along with EMD to achieve better noise suppression but at the cost of increasing the overall complexity of the algorithm.

A better enhancement to this method was presented in [26] in the form of complete ensemble empirical mode decomposition which uses approximately half the number of shifting operations and therefore can minimize the computational cost of the algorithm [26]. However, the baseline wander is not corrected and must be processed further. Moving median filters were used in [27] and mean-median filtering along with DWT was used in [28] to remove the baseline wander. This yields better results for noise cancellation than other methods. The use of moving average filters was presented in [29] to suppress powerline interference. Apart from these, machine learning approaches to detect QRS are found in [30]–[35]. These algorithms use deep learning and convolution neural networks to classify the beats and the noise. In [36], [37], algorithms are based on simple learning and transformations that can be easily implemented without machine learning usage. Kalman filters were used for QRS detection in [38] while they

were used along with adaptive thresholding to detect peaks in [39]. Since all these methods rely on heavy-duty processing to reduce noises and then adaptive thresholding to detect peaks, the relation between computational complexity and performance is quite the opposite.

In this paper, we present a simple statistical approach for detecting QRS without using any computationally intensive filtering or transformations. Here, we propose a novel technique based on median and moving average (MA) filters along with considering the mean of R-R, as a portion of the segment, as a threshold. The use of median filters stabilizes the baseline wander and minimizes the amplitudes of the P and T waves while moving average filtering gets rid of high amplitude electrical noise. Segmentation and Statistical False Peak Elimination (SFPE) are used to detect true R-peaks and remove falsely detected noise peaks. Search back is used to detect any low amplitude true R-peaks missed during the detection.

2. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The electrocardiogram (ECG) is a non-invasive test for the heart which is conducted by placing electrodes on the chest to record the electrical activity of the heart. It contains P waves, QRS complex and T waves. R peaks are prominent features in the ECG signal. The signal obtained has large amounts of noise components which makes the R-peak detection very challenging.

Due to noise, they are quite often suppressed and cannot be detected properly without removing the noise contaminating the sample. The Haar wavelet transform is a popular signal processing algorithm that is frequently used in electrocardiogram (ECG) analysis. It is a type of discrete wavelet transform that can be used to decompose a signal into a set of wavelet coefficients at different scales and locations. In ECG analysis, the Haar wavelet transform can be used to identify important features of the ECG signal, such as the QRS complex, the P wave, and the T wave. These features can be used to diagnose various cardiac conditions, such as arrhythmias, ischemia, and infarction.

Sources of noise are power-line interference, electrode contact noise, contraction of muscles, noise produced from electronic devices and external electrical interference such as recording systems, baseline wander, and bodily sounds such as breathing, stomach or bowel sounds. All these unwanted artifacts make the detection

of R-peaks quite challenging to date. These noise components are reduced by using the different filtering techniques and to find the true R-peaks in the signal. In this method we are using Discrete Wavelet Transform algorithm.

2.1 Block Diagram of the proposed system

Figure 1: Block diagram of the proposed system

ECG Signal

It is a graphical record of bioelectrical signal generated by human body during cardiac cycle. It is the input signal. It is given to the noise filtering block as it is required to remove the noise from the signal.

Figure 2: ECG Signal

Signal Denoising

It is the process of removing the unwanted data from the required.

ECG Segmentation

ECG segmentation (Figure 4) is the process of dividing an ECG signal into smaller, non-overlapping segments, each of which corresponds to a specific interval or waveform of the cardiac cycle.

Figure 3: ECG Segmentation

The process of down-sampling is that what produces the DWT coefficients which are the approximation coefficients obtained from the low pass filter and the detail coefficients obtained from the high pass filter. A multi level wavelet decomposition tree is obtained by further decomposition process for the approximation coefficients, so that one signal is broken down into many lower resolution components.

Wavelet transform is a powerful tool for feature extraction of ECG signals. The basic idea behind wavelet transform is to decompose the signal into different frequency sub-bands using wavelet basis functions. The decomposition process involves scaling and translation of the wavelet basis function to obtain a set of coefficients at different scales and positions. These coefficients represent the signal energy at different frequency bands, which can be used as features for ECG signal analysis. The main idea is the same as it is in the DWT. A time-scale representation of a digital signal is obtained using digital filtering techniques. Recall that the DWT is a correlation between a wavelet at different scales and the signal with the scale being used as a measure of similarity.

The original signal $x[n]$ is first passed through a half-band high-pass filter $g[n]$ and a half-band low-pass filter $h[n]$. After filtering, half of the samples can be eliminated according to Nyquist's rule, since the signal now has a highest frequency of $\pi/2$ radians instead of π . The signal can therefore be **downsampled** by a factor of 2, simply by discarding every other sample. This process constitutes one level of **wavelet decomposition** and can mathematically be expressed as follows:

$$y_{high}[k] = \sum_n x[n] \cdot g[2k - n]$$

$$y_{low}[k] = \sum_n x[n] \cdot h[2k - n]$$

Where $y_{high}[k]$ and $y_{low}[k]$ are the outputs of the high-pass and low-pass filters, respectively, after sub-sampling by 2.

For filtering the signal, different types of filters are used. In **Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT)** (Figure 4), the original signal passes through two filters:

- A **low-pass filter**, which produces the approximation coefficients $h[n]$, representing the most important part of the signal.
- A **high-pass filter**, which produces the detail coefficients $g[n]$, capturing the high-frequency components.

Here, these two functions are called **scaling functions** and **wavelet functions**, respectively

Figure 4: Process of Discrete Wavelet Transform

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The MIT-BIH Long-Term ECG Database serves as a standard benchmark for evaluating arrhythmia detection algorithms. It comprises 18 long-duration recordings of 24-hour ambulatory ECG data, covering both normal and abnormal heart rhythms. This dataset is instrumental in the development and validation of automatic ECG analysis techniques.

Figure 5: ECG signal is a graphical representation of the electrical activity of the heart over time

Figure 5 illustrates a typical ECG signal, which represents the electrical activity of the heart over time. The signal is captured using surface electrodes that measure voltage fluctuations caused by the heart's electrical impulses during each beat.

To enhance the quality of ECG signals, noise reduction techniques are employed. The effectiveness of these techniques is evaluated using the Signal-to-Error Ratio (SER), which compares the original signal with the processed version. As shown in Figure 6, the SER value provides a quantitative measure of noise reduction performance.

Figure 6. SER value quantifies ECG noise reduction effectiveness

Wavelet-based signal processing techniques have been applied to further enhance the ECG signal quality. Figure 7 presents the SER values obtained using the Wavelet transform method, which decomposes the ECG signal into different frequency components. This technique aids in preserving critical diagnostic information while effectively reducing noise.

Figure 7: SER value for ECG signal quality assessment using the Wavelet method

These results highlight the significance of advanced signal processing methods in improving ECG signal quality, thereby enhancing the accuracy of arrhythmia detection algorithms.

ADVANTAGES

- SER is low.
- Operation is fast.
- Complexity is less.
- In-Built filters are present.
- Accuracy is more.

APPLICATIONS

- In Electrocardiogram device.
- In ECG biometrics.

3. CONCLUSION

In this paper, QRS detection using a simple statistical analysis of the ECG signal has been presented. Discrete Wavelet Transform algorithm and Haar Wavelet algorithm have been considered in this paper for effective detection of QRS complexes. Dividing the record into multiple segments resulted in low processing time and better accuracy. Furthermore, eliminating false peaks, identified very few false positives and therefore have shown better positive predictivity than other methods mentioned in the paper. We have analysed the output with the previous models. Simulation results have shown better performance in most of the records than other methods. Thus, the proposed algorithm performs better in terms of automatic detection with a higher percentage of overall detection rate.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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